

Mother Teresa – An Icon of Woman Empowerment

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Abstract

She was meek and fragile, but established and headed a global religious community. She was humble in spirit, but dared to touch, nurse and serve the wounded lepers, from whom the world walked away. She opened the door of mercy and unceasing love to the dying and the destitute on the streets, to whom the world shut its doors. She walked through paths of thorns and roads of chaos, but had clear plans to reach her destiny. Her clean smile on a wrinkled face, won the hearts of her opponents. She preferred an unnoticed and quiet life, but the world turned its eyes on her. She came as a foreigner to India, but stands today as an honor and pride of India. Merely a channel of peace and love? No, Not just. She is a sign of daring valor, undying courage and magnanimity. She is Mother Teresa, Mother of millions, a Nobel Laureate, a Saint, an Inspiration and an Icon of Woman Empowerment.

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Starting from the stone-age to the space age of this day, Man has worked to make his existence on this planet a comfortable and luxurious place. Further, his search for a new planet which supports life has been in gear for a long time. In spite of his brainy inventions and peaking ‘satellite eyes’, the earth still remains to be a unique and unparalleled gift in the universe.

Man, who knew to make this a more comfortable and luxurious planet, failed to make it a place of peace. By sowing the seeds of rivalry, selfishness, envy, greed and indiscipline, he has reaped poverty and violence. Only a small percent of people enjoy their existence on earth and the others are deprived of it. The real need of today’s world is not advancements in technology but making earth a truly gifted and unique planet for every life in it.

History points out many great men and women who have strived to do this. The Sainly Mother Teresa, the Nobel laureate for peace, is unique among them and stands as an inspiration and symbol of woman empowerment. Striving and living for a good cause requires immense courage. With a small-built and meek appearance, she was a woman of great inner strength and unbreakable will power.

Born on August 26 to pious and righteous Albanian couple and baptized as Agnes Gonxhe Bojaxhiu, she found her religious calling and became a Christian nun. She came to India in 1929 and served as a teacher in Darjeeling and then in Calcutta. For almost twenty years. Mother Teresa dedicated her life as a teacher at the St Mary’s School,

graduating to the post of the principal in 1944. Her undaunted commitment to serve the society and mankind was greatly recognized by students and teachers. Though she enjoyed teaching young girls, she was greatly disturbed by the poverty and misery that was prevalent in Calcutta.

During her journey from Calcutta to Darjeeling she experienced another call from God asking her to establish a society for serving the poorest of the poor. She determined to do this although it seemed to be impossible. Here began a test for her determination and strength. It was not easy to get permission from her religious community as she had already taken her final profession of vows in a community called Sisters of Loreto. She neither rebelled nor gave up. Her exceptional patience and perseverance convinced her religious superiors and finally her dream came true on October 7, 1950, a historic day in the life of Mother Teresa when she finally received permission from the Vatican to start the congregation known as Missionaries of Charity.

Clad in a white blue-bordered saree, Mother Teresa began her journey to reach the unreachable star, to win the unbeatable foe, to love the unloved, to touch the untouchables, to serve the abandoned and to comfort the uncared. With a strong determination and unflinching courage, she entered the world of poor, a world that needed her, a world of her own!

With no big plans, not much money and with merely thirteen members she started the journey to accomplish her vision. With a humble beginning, the Missionaries of Charity became one of the most significant and recognized congregations in the world under the dynamic leadership of Mother Teresa.

Mother Teresa opened her first home for the sick, destitute and the dying in Kalighat, Kolkata with help from Indian officials after much struggle. Known as the Kalighat Home for the Dying, provided medical attention to those in need and it gave people the opportunity to die with dignity in accordance with their faith. In the words of Mother Teresa, it was “for people who lived like animals to die like angels — loved and wanted”.

In 1955, Teresa’s Missionaries of Charity opened Nirmala Shishu Bhavan, the Children’s Home to take care of homeless children and provided them with food, shelter and medical care.

True bravery is to walk where the brave dare not go. Mother Teresa exhibited this rare valor and undying spirit by starting Shanti Nagar, a home for lepers. In India, a large number of people were infected with leprosy, a disease that can lead to major disfiguration. Mother Teresa created a Leprosy Fund and a Leprosy Day to help educate the public about leprosy as many people feared the contagious disease. She also established several mobile leper clinics to provide the infected with medicine and bandages near their home.

Missionaries of Charity had almost 4000 sisters working in 610 foundations, in 450 centres in 123 countries across the six continents. The congregation had several hospices and homes for people with HIV/AIDS, leprosy and tuberculosis, soup kitchens, children’s and family counselling programs, personal helpers, orphanages, and schools functioning under it.

“Those who humble themselves will be exalted” – Jesus Christ. The humble and meek Mother Teresa was bestowed with highest National and International awards and honors. The Government of India honored her with Padma Shri, Jawaharlal Nehru Award for International Understanding and Bharat Ratna, India’s highest civilian award. She was honoured with Ramon Magsaysay Award for International Understanding, for her merciful cognizance of the abject poor of a foreign land, in whose service she led a new congregation. In 1971, she was awarded the first Pope John XXIII Peace Prize for her work with the poor, display of Christian charity and efforts for peace. In 1979, Mother Teresa was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize, “for work undertaken in the struggle to overcome poverty and distress, which also constitutes a threat to peace.” During her lifetime, Mother Teresa was among the top 10 women in the annual Gallup’s most admired man and woman poll 18 times. In 1999, Mother Teresa ranked first in Gallup’s List of Most Widely Admired People of the 20th Century.

And above all, she has been canonized as a saint, by the Vatican. Declaring a person as a saint by the Catholic church is only after a grueling process, involving volumes of historical research, the hunt for miracles and teams of experts to weigh the evidence.

Mother Teresa is a big sign of woman empowerment. Being a woman, Mother Teresa accomplished her great vision, by mostly women in her mission, though she was rendered support from men of good will. She gave hope for her sisters in a hopeless situation. Her life, which was devoted to helping people in need, led to many others joining her mission of serving the poor. Her Holy journey, which was thorny and painful, faced many hurdles from men of religious and political influence. She faced hurting humiliation when she went asking for alms for her poor people. With just a smile on her wrinkled face, she won not only won the hearts of men who opposed her but also made them support her. With her unparalleled patience, she set right the unrightable wrong.

Looked upon as a channel of peace and love, the Saint Mother Teresa is surely a source of hope and inspiration, a symbol of dynamic courage and great valor, not only to women but to men as well.

“It is not how much we do,
but how much love we put in the doing.

It is not how much we give,
but how much love we put in the giving.”

“Not all of us can do great things. But we can do small things with great love.”

-Mother Teresa

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